

Multi-Source Collaborative Identification of AS Border Routers via Cyberspace Mapping Engines

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Abstract—Accurate identification of Autonomous System (AS) border routers—including vendor, model, and firmware version—is critical for routing security assessment and inter-domain traffic engineering. Existing fingerprinting techniques rely primarily on initial TTL (iTTL) signatures or SNMPv3 probing, yet both suffer from structural blind spots: iTTL signatures cannot distinguish Cisco IOS from Huawei VRP, while SNMPv3 achieves only 15–18% response rates due to widespread port filtering. This paper proposes a multi-source collaborative identification framework that systematically introduces cyberspace mapping engines (FOFA, Shodan, Censys, ZoomEye) as a third fingerprint source, complementing LFP and SNMPv3 through a unified three-level model matching pipeline and a Weighted Confidence Fusion Algorithm (WCFA) with context-aware dynamic weight adjustment. Experiments on 1,500 border routers across three geographic regions demonstrate that the tri-source fusion raises vendor identification coverage from approximately 65% to 79.4%, and WCFA achieves 91.3% resolution accuracy on 188 conflicting cases—a 7.6 percentage-point improvement over simple priority-based arbitration. Nearly half of covered routers receive model-level identification, and over one quarter obtain complete vendor-model-firmware triplets.

Keywords—AS border router, device fingerprinting, cyberspace mapping engine, multi-source fusion, weighted confidence

I. INTRODUCTION

AS border routers serve as critical hubs for inter-domain communication, directly affecting global network reachability and stability. Recent disclosures of vendor-specific vulnerabilities [1] and supply-chain security restrictions have made vendor identification and model-level characterization of these routers an important research topic in network security. For the BGP community-attribute-based traffic steering method proposed in Chapter V of this thesis, knowing the device model and capability of key eBGP border routers along the steering path is a necessary prerequisite for determining whether they support the required community attribute policy execution.

Two primary fingerprinting approaches exist. The LFP (Lightweight Fingerprinting) method [2] constructs a three-dimensional iTTL signature vector from ICMP, TCP, and UDP responses, achieving 60–70% coverage but suffering from a fundamental ambiguity: Cisco IOS and Huawei VRP share identical signatures (255,255,-). The SNMPv3 approach [3] extracts Engine ID and sysDeser from discovery responses with >98% precision, but only 15–18% of border routers respond due to widespread SNMP port filtering. Both approaches share a structural blind spot for routers that expose SSH, Telnet, or HTTPS management interfaces but neither SNMPv3 nor distinguishable iTTL signatures.

Meanwhile, cyberspace mapping engines such as Shodan [4], Censys [5], FOFA [6], and ZoomEye [7] have accumulated extensive banner records from these management ports through continuous Internet-wide scanning, yet no prior work has systematically applied them to AS border router identification.

In the broader context of device fingerprinting, Sun [8] proposed passive (BEMFNet deep learning model), active (state machine inference via model learning), and collaborative methods for IPsec implementation identification, achieving 97.28% F1-score on 8 IPsec implementations. While this demonstrates that Cisco and Huawei implementations are distinguishable at the protocol interaction level [9], IPsec fingerprinting requires target devices to expose IKE services (UDP 500/4500) and identifies protocol implementations rather than device models—limiting its applicability to large-scale border router identification [10].

This paper makes three contributions: systematic introduction of mapping engines as a third fingerprint source for AS border routers; a unified three-level model matching pipeline that standardizes heterogeneous fingerprint signals into comparable five-tuple identifiers; a Weighted Confidence Fusion Algorithm (WCFA) with context-aware ambiguity demotion and cross-engine consistency promotion.

II. MULTI-SOURCE COLLABORATIVE IDENTIFICATION METHOD

A. Overall Pipeline

The method processes each target IP through four sequential steps, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The core contribution lies not in inventing new fingerprint acquisition techniques, but in three levels of systematic engineering innovation: first introducing mapping engines into AS border router identification; designing a unified matching pipeline; and proposing WCFA for conflict resolution.

Fig. 1. Overall pipeline of the multi-source collaborative identification method.

Step 1 (Date Target Confirmation): Given a target interface IP, the system queries the AS topology knowledge graph (Date,

built in Chapter III) to confirm the IP belongs to an eBGP border router, retrieving AS number, tier level, and geographic region. This context informs subsequent steps—e.g., if the AS is in China, Step 3 will prioritize FOFA and ZoomEye over Shodan.

Step 2 (LFP Passive Signature Extraction): The system retrieves archived traceroute records from CAIDA Ark's ITDK dataset (covering 2.9M router interface IPs) rather than conducting active probing, for two reasons: ITDK coverage far exceeds what the authors could achieve independently; and reusing archived data avoids triggering intrusion detection systems. The received TTL and initial iTTL satisfy:

$$TTL_{rcv} = iTTL - h_{rev}$$

LFP estimates the reverse hop count via multi-path topology inference and recovers the true iTTL, constructing a three-dimensional signature vector:

$$\mathbf{V}_{sig} = \langle iTTL_{ICMP}, iTTL_{TCP}, iTTL_{UDP} \rangle$$

The vector is matched against the known signature table (Table I).

TABLE I. iTTL SIGNATURE VECTORS OF MAINSTREAM BORDER ROUTER PLATFORMS

Cisco IOS/IOS XR: $\langle 255,255,- \rangle$ — overlaps with Huawei VRP. Huawei VRP: $\langle 255,255,- \rangle$ — overlaps with Cisco IOS. Juniper JunOS: $\langle 255,64,255 \rangle$ — unique signature. Linux-based (VyOS/OpenWRT): $\langle 64,64,64 \rangle$ — overlaps with MikroTik. MikroTik RouterOS: $\langle 64,64,64 \rangle$ — overlaps with Linux-based.

Three outcomes arise: (a) unique match (e.g., Juniper)—output with weight 0.65, skip to Step 4; (b) ambiguity zone (Cisco/Huawei)—weight demoted from 0.65 to 0.50, must continue to Step 3; (c) no CAIDA Ark record—output "no information", continue to Step 3. This step serves as a high-coverage coarse screening baseline (60–70% coverage).

Comparison with protocol-layer fingerprinting: Sun's BEMFNet [8] demonstrated that Cisco and Huawei exhibit distinguishable differences at the IPsec IKE negotiation level (F1=97.28%). However, for our large-scale scenario (2.9M interface IPs), IPsec fingerprinting faces three applicability limitations: not all border routers expose IPsec services; active IKE negotiation raises compliance concerns; and its identification granularity is "protocol implementation" (e.g., strongSwan) rather than "device model + firmware version" (e.g., Cisco ASR 9000, IOS XR 7.3.1). We therefore chose a tri-source parallel approach requiring no target cooperation.

Step 3 (Parallel Evidence Acquisition): Two routes execute concurrently.

Route A (SNMPv3 Single-Packet Probing): The system sends an unauthenticated SNMPv3 Discovery packet to UDP 161 (timeout 3s, 2 retries). If the router responds, the Report PDU contains an Engine ID whose first four bytes encode the IEEE vendor enterprise number (OUI)—e.g., 0x00000009 = Cisco, 0x000007DB = Huawei—enabling direct vendor mapping (>98% precision). Further querying sysDescr yields complete model and firmware information (Fig. 2). Since

Engine ID is firmware-hardcoded with no spoofing incentive, SNMPv3 weight is set to 0.95 (highest among three sources), and valid responses trigger short-circuit output. However, measured response rate is only 15–18%, meaning ~84% of IPs must rely on other routes.

Fig. 2. SNMPv3 Engine ID structure and OUI-to-vendor mapping.

Route B (Mapping Engine Banner Query): Concurrently, the system queries FOFA, Shodan, and Censys APIs using the target IP as key, retrieving historical scan records. Three types of fingerprint signals are extracted (Fig. 3): (i) service banners—SSH banner version strings identify OS type, Telnet welcome messages may contain complete model and firmware version; (ii) SSL/TLS certificates—HTTPS management interface certificate Subject fields may contain product series names; (iii) native engine fingerprint tags—FOFA's 350K fingerprint rules directly output structured device classifications.

Fig. 3. Three types of fingerprint signals extracted from mapping engines.

Three adaptation strategies are designed for this step. First, China-priority engine selection: Chen et al. [9] showed that ~67% of FOFA and ~72% of ZoomEye scan source IPs are located in China, providing higher coverage for Chinese network assets; since these routers are precisely the group where LFP ambiguity is most severe (China-region precision only 62.3%), we prioritize FOFA/ZoomEye for Chinese ASes. Second, cross-engine consistency verification: if two or more engines return the same vendor for one IP, weight is promoted from 0.75 to 0.85; if contradictory, only the most recent and highest-scoring record is retained with weight demoted to 0.65. Third, DNS hostname auxiliary verification: if reverse DNS yields a hostname containing explicit model keywords (e.g., ne40e, asr9k), it is included in the evidence set with weight 0.90.

Step 4 (Evidence Aggregation and Standardization): After the above three steps, the system has collected heterogeneous fingerprint evidence from three routes for each target IP. All evidence passes through the three-level model matching pipeline (§II-B) to be standardized into five-tuples (interface IP, vendor name, device model, firmware version, confidence level) before entering the WCFA conflict resolution algorithm (§II-C).

TABLE II summarizes the role positioning of the three routes: LFP serves as the high-coverage coarse screening baseline (60–70%, weight 0.65/0.50); SNMPv3 provides high-precision anchoring with short-circuit priority (15–18%, weight 0.95); mapping engines handle ambiguity resolution and blind spot coverage (12–18%, weight 0.75/0.85/0.65). The overall design embodies a "coarse-to-fine, progressive disambiguation" strategy.

B. Three-Level Model Matching

Raw fingerprint signals from three routes are heterogeneous in format. Our matching pipeline standardizes them through three stages: signal preprocessing, three-level model matching, and result standardization, as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Three-level model matching pipeline.

In the preprocessing stage, LFP outputs are matched against the signature table to return vendor candidate sets; SNMPv3 outputs are parsed for OUI via IEEE database lookup while retaining sysDescr text; mapping engine outputs undergo charset cleaning for banners, Subject field extraction for SSL certificates, and direct vendor/product field reading for structured API responses.

The three-level matching operates in descending precision with a stop-on-hit strategy. Level 1 (Exact Model Matching): a 156-entry keyword-to-standard-model mapping table covering Cisco, Huawei, Juniper, and Nokia product lines (e.g., ASR9K/asr9000-s/ASR 9001 all map to Cisco ASR 9000). Level 2 (Vendor + Series Matching): vendor name variants combined with product series keywords (e.g., Juniper Networks + MX → Juniper MX series). Level 3 (Protocol Format Weak Inference): five distinctive banner format patterns—OpenSSH format → Linux-based; "Cisco IOS Software" prefix → Cisco IOS; "Huawei Versatile Routing Platform" → Huawei VRP; "JUNOS" → JunOS; "TiMOS" → Nokia SR OS. If all three levels fail, the signal is marked invalid and excluded from fusion.

After matching, results are standardized into five-tuples: interface IP, vendor name (normalized to CAIDA conventions), device model (mapped to internal standard identifier), firmware version (preserved from parsed signal), and confidence level.

C. Weighted Confidence Fusion Algorithm

When multiple routes produce inconsistent vendor identifications for the same router, the system faces a heterogeneous data source conflict resolution problem. Naive

priority-based polling loses cumulative evidence from lower-confidence sources; equal-weight voting ignores fundamental reliability differences across measurement protocols. We propose WCFA, whose decision flow is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. WCFA decision flowchart.

Formal definition: Let the target router set be $R = \{r_1, \dots, r_n\}$, candidate vendor set $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_k\}$, and data source set $S = \{s_{LFP}, s_{SNMP}, s_{Map}, s_{DNS}\}$. Each source s_j is assigned a base confidence weight w_j :

$$\mathbf{W} = [w_{LFP}, w_{SNMP}, w_{Map}, w_{DNS}] = [0.65, 0.95, 0.75, 0.90]$$

Weights are context-aware: LFP ambiguity demotion (w_{LFP} : 0.65 → 0.50) when signatures enter the Cisco/Huawei overlap zone; cross-engine consistency promotion (w_{Map} : 0.75 → 0.85) when ≥ 2 independent engines concur.

The support function $F(s_j, v_m)$ quantifies each source's evidence, mapped to discrete values:

$$F(s_j, v_m) \in \{-0.5, 0, 0.5, 1.0\}$$

Where: explicit support ($F=1.0$), partial support ($F=0.5$, e.g., overlapping signature candidates), no information ($F=0.0$), and explicit opposition ($F=-0.5$). The composite confidence score is:

$$Score(v_m) = \sum_{s_j \in S} w_j \cdot F(s_j, v_m)$$

The final output maximizes the score:

$$v^* = \operatorname{argmax}_{v_m \in V} Score(v_m)$$

Confidence levels are assigned by absolute score:

$$L_{conf} = \begin{cases} High, & Score(v^*) \geq 1.5 \\ Medium, & 0.8 \leq Score(v^*) < 1.5 \\ Low, & Score(v^*) < 0.8 \end{cases}$$

Short-circuit evaluation precedes weighted fusion: (1) if SNMPv3 Engine ID is valid, directly output as High; (2) if DNS hostname contains exact model keyword with no contradiction, output; (3) otherwise, execute full weighted computation.

Case study: A router in a Chinese AS (IP anonymized as 202.97.*.*). s_{LFP} : iTTL=(255,255,-), ambiguous (F=0.5 for both Cisco and Huawei, $w=0.50$ after demotion). s_{SNMP} : UDP 161 timeout (F=0.0). s_{DNS} : hostname ne40e-0.bj01.as4134.cn (F=-0.5 for Cisco, F=1.0 for Huawei, $w=0.90$). s_{Map} : FOFA + ZoomEye both return Huawei with cross-engine consistency (F=-0.5 for Cisco, F=1.0 for Huawei, $w=0.85$ after promotion). Computation:

$$Score(Cisco) = 0.50 \times 0.5 + 0.90 \times (-0.5) + 0.85 \times (-0.5) = -0.625$$

$$Score(Huawei) = 0.50 \times 0.5 + 0.90 \times 1.0 + 0.85 \times 1.0 = 2.00$$

Verdict: $v^* = \text{Huawei}$, $Score = 2.00 \geq 1.5$, confidence = High. This demonstrates how WCFA leverages cumulative weak evidence from upper-layer sources (DNS, mapping engine certificates) to resolve ambiguity in lower-layer probing protocols.

III. EXPERIMENTS AND ANALYSIS

A. Experimental Setup

Experiments use the CAIDA ITDK October 2025 snapshot (~2.9M router interface IPs, ~610K border routers via bdrmapIT [10]). We randomly sample 500 border routers from each of three regions (China, North America, Western Europe), totaling 1,500, to ensure regional representativeness. LFP fingerprint data is extracted from CAIDA Ark traceroute archives without active probing. SNMPv3 probing was conducted January–February 2026 (timeout 3s, 2 retries per IP). Mapping engine data was queried via FOFA, Shodan, and Censys APIs within the same time window (ZoomEye used only for China region due to API quota limits). DNS reverse resolution was performed via recursive queries to each IP's authoritative DNS. All data acquisition was completed within February 2026 for temporal consistency.

Table 1 Overview of Experimental Setup

Item	Details
LFP Data	iTTL from CAIDA Ark archive, no active probing
SNMPv3	Jan-Feb 2026, 3s timeout \times 2 retries
Engine Query	FOFA+Shodan+Censys same window (ZoomEye China only)
DNS	Recursive to authoritative DNS
Metric 1	Coverage: IPs with \geq vendor-level ID
Metric 2	Precision: vendor/model vs. manual ground truth
Metric 3	Exclusive: only identifiable by this source

Three evaluation metrics are used: (1) coverage rate—proportion of IPs receiving at least vendor-level identification; (2) identification precision—vendor-level and model-level precision against manually verified ground truth (30 randomly sampled results per source per region, cross-verified via SNMPv3 sysDescr, engine banner text, and BGP route announcements); (3) exclusive contribution rate—proportion of routers identifiable only by that source, quantifying each route's irreplaceability.

B. Coverage and Precision Analysis

Table 2 Comparison of Coverage and Accuracy of Three Types of Data Sources

Source	Coverage	Vendor Prec.	Model Cap.	Limitation
LFP iTTL	60-70%	Medium	None	Cisco/Huawei Signature overlap
SNMP v3	15-20%	Very high(98%+)	Exact	Low availability
Engine s	12-18%	Med-high	Model - capability	Uneven freq.
Tri-source	~79%	High	Model - capability	Multi-API needed

The tri-source fusion achieves 79.4% weighted-average vendor identification coverage (China: 77.4%, North America: 81.2%, Western Europe: 79.6%), a ~15 percentage-point improvement over LFP alone (~65%). LFP maintains 60–70% coverage across all three regions but vendor precision in China is only 62.3%, significantly lower than North America (89.5%) and Western Europe (91.2%) due to the Cisco/Huawei signature overlap and higher Huawei deployment ratio in China. SNMPv3 response rates range 15–18% across all regions with >98% vendor precision and 94% model-level precision. Mapping engine coverage ranges 12–18%, highest in China (18.3%), consistent with FOFA/ZoomEye's scanning bias toward Chinese assets.

The mapping engine's exclusive contribution rate is highest in China (7.8%)—meaning 7.8% of Chinese border routers can only be vendor-identified through engine banners, while LFP outputs ambiguous results and SNMPv3 has no record. This exclusive contribution is 5.1% in North America and 4.3% in Western Europe, confirming the mapping engine's effective coverage of traditional methods' blind spots.

C. Conflict Resolution and Model Identification

Among the 1,500 sample routers, 188 (12.5%) exhibit multi-source conflicts. The dominant conflict type is LFP(Cisco) vs. mapping-engine(Huawei), accounting for 112 cases concentrated in China, entirely consistent with LFP's known limitation in the signature overlap scenario. The second most common type is DNS hostname pointing to one model while the mapping engine points to a different vendor (49 cases), mostly due to hostname not being updated after equipment replacement (Fig. 7).

WCFA achieves 91.3% resolution accuracy on these 188 conflict cases, compared to 83.7% for simple priority-based arbitration—a 7.6 percentage-point improvement. The improvement comes from two scenarios: (a) when SNMPv3 has no response but mapping engines show cross-engine consistency and DNS hostname supports the same vendor, the weighted algorithm correctly reflects cumulative weak

evidence; (b) when LFP has signature ambiguity, the mapping engine's higher-confidence result is correctly prioritized.

Model-level identification is the core capability extension over LFP. Among 1,191 covered routers, 580 (48.7%) receive specific model identification: 274 from SNMPv3 sysDescr (18.3%), 238 from mapping engine banner parsing (15.9%), 153 from DNS hostname model keywords (10.2%). LFP's model-level capability is zero—the fundamental motivation for introducing other sources. In mapping-engine-contributed model IDs, Cisco devices are primarily ASR 9000 (41.2%) and 7600 (23.8%); Juniper primarily MX (55.3%) and PTX (18.7%); Huawei primarily NE40E (62.1%) and CR (22.4%). Approximately 28.1% of covered routers obtain complete vendor-model-firmware triplets.

D. Regional Variation Analysis

Regional network environments significantly affect data source effectiveness (Fig. 9). In China, the mapping engine's exclusive contribution is most prominent due to FOFA/ZoomEye's geographic scanning bias [9] and the prevalence of Huawei equipment creating maximal LFP ambiguity. In North America and Western Europe, Shodan and Censys provide more comprehensive coverage, and operators' DNS hostname naming conventions are more mature, yielding stronger DNS route contributions. Multi-engine parallel querying effectively balances regional coverage differences.

E. Comparison with Protocol-Layer Fingerprinting

Table III compares our method with Sun's IPsec fingerprinting [8] to clarify the rationale for our technical choice—this comparison aims to illustrate complementarity rather than simple superiority. Our method offers large-scale applicability (2.9M IPs) without requiring target cooperation, achieving 79.4% coverage and 91.3% conflict resolution accuracy; IPsec fingerprinting achieves finer-grained implementation-level distinction (F1=97.28%) for devices exposing IKE services but is limited to medium-scale scenarios requiring per-device interaction. A cascaded strategy—tri-source coarse screening followed by protocol-layer fine identification on IPsec-enabled subsets (quickly filterable via mapping engines for UDP 500 exposure)—is a promising future direction that could achieve both large-scale coverage and fine-grained identification.

Table 3 Comparison of the method in this paper with the IPsec protocol fingerprinting method

Dimension	This Paper	IPsec (Sun [8])
Target	Vendor/model/FW	Protocol impl.
Requirement	No cooperation	IPsec required
Method	iTTL+SNMPv3+API	Passive+active IKE
Scale	Large (2.9M IPs)	Medium (per-device)
Cisco/Huawei Strength	Fusion (91.3%) High coverage, model ID	Direct (F1=97.28%) High precision, same-vendor
Limitation	Needs external sources	Requires IPsec

F. Experimental Conclusions

Three conclusions emerge: First, tri-source fusion improves coverage by ~15 pp over LFP alone, validating the multi-source synergy strategy. Mapping engines provide device information for 12–18% of border router IPs that traditional methods cannot reach. Second, WCFA improves conflict resolution accuracy by 7.6 pp over priority-based arbitration, demonstrating the substantive decision value of cumulative weak evidence. Third, model-level identification capability—absent in LFP—is the core contribution: nearly half of covered routers receive model-level conclusions, and over one quarter receive complete triplet identification.

Limitations include: mapping engine API quota constraints for large-scale deployment; banner parsing robustness depending on continuous regex rule library maintenance; and growing anti-fingerprinting measures (modified default iTTL values, closed management ports, filtered ICMP responses) applying persistent pressure on all routes' coverage rates.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a multi-source collaborative framework for AS border router identification that systematically integrates cyberspace mapping engines with LFP and SNMPv3 fingerprinting. Through a "coarse-to-fine, progressive disambiguation" four-step pipeline—Date target confirmation, LFP coarse screening, parallel SNMPv3/mapping-engine precision acquisition, and WCFA conflict resolution—the framework achieves 79.4% vendor coverage and 91.3% conflict resolution accuracy on 1,500 border routers across three geographic regions, with nearly half receiving model-level and over one quarter receiving complete triplet identification.

The framework forms an upstream-downstream synergy with the Date knowledge graph (Chapter III): Date provides target search space constraints, while the device asset graph produced by this chapter will provide target node knowledge for the traffic steering framework (Chapter V). Additionally, this method complements protocol-layer fingerprinting approaches [8] at a different granularity level—our method for large-scale vendor/model identification, protocol-layer methods for finer implementation-level distinction. Their cascaded use represents a promising avenue for enhancing device identification completeness in future work.

V. REFERENCES

- [1] T. Albakour, O. Gasser, R. Beverly, et al., "Illuminating router vendor diversity within providers and along network paths," in Proc. ACM IMC, 2023, pp. 1–15.
- [2] T. Albakour, O. Gasser, R. Beverly, et al., "Third time's not a charm: Exploiting SNMPv3 for router fingerprinting," in Proc. ACM IMC, 2021, pp. 150–164.
- [3] D. Harrington, R. Presuhn, and B. Wijnen, "An architecture for describing SNMP management frameworks," RFC 3411, IETF, 2002.
- [4] J. Matherly, Complete Guide to Shodan. Shodan, 2017.
- [5] Z. Durumeric, D. Adrian, A. Mirian, et al., "A search engine backed by Internet-wide scanning," in Proc. ACM CCS, 2015, pp. 542–553.
- [6] FOFA Team, "FOFA: Cyberspace assets search engine," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://fofa.info/>
- [7] KnownSec 404 Team, "ZoomEye: Cyberspace search engine," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.zoomeye.org/>

- [8] X. Sun, "Research on fingerprint identification technology for IPsec protocol implementations," M.S. thesis, Information Engineering Univ., 2025.
- [9] X. Chen, J. Zhang, Z. Li, et al., "Revealing the black box of device search engines," in Proc. NDSS, 2025, pp. 1–17.
- [10] A. Marder, M. Luckie, A. Dhamdhere, et al., "Pushing the boundaries with bdrmapIT: Mapping router ownership at Internet scale," in Proc. ACM IMC, 2018, pp. 414–421.